

Strengths and Limitations of Different Teaching Modes: A Comparative Study

Mili Saha*
Md. Ali Rezwon Talukdar*

Abstract: Whether in language teaching or elsewhere, sustainable attainment of a pedagogical goal is closely related to a successful teaching mode. In a bid to have a gambit in a teaching procedure with a proper choice of a teaching mode, a teacher is expected to be well acquainted with the strengths and limitations of the prevailing teaching modes. Regarding this, over the years researchers have made efforts in exploring the immense ideological horizons, while in our country, still, lecture mode is the most commonly found one. Along with making thorough study of different aspects of various teaching modes, this current study scrutinizes some practical cases and examples in the academic context of Bangladesh. It attempts to recommend the optimum success level of lecture mode and to which extent lecture mode needs to be alternated or to be assimilated with others as well as how to minimize the weakness of it and ensure the maximum potentiality of the other teaching modes, basing on the established ideas in this field and the empirical studies done by these authors.

1. Introduction

It would not be an exaggeration while making the statement that a successful teaching mode is both the root and route of achieving educational goal while an ineffectual one may be the same to detriment that goal. But, in most of the cases, we find, especially in our country, in spite of being aware of the fact, the concerns are almost failed to bring a proper teaching mode before the learners. And, that's why, the exact accomplishment of students' learning that is aspired through the pedagogy often remains out of grasp.

We should rather say that one of the striking features of our education programs is the restricted range of teaching and learning modes utilized here. In most cases, even in higher education, the dominant teaching mode is formal lecture, backed up by some progressive tests like tutorials or in course exams in some cases.

According to Micheal J. Wallace, "The reason for certain modes being dominant: often it is a matter of "unthinking tradition" (this is the way it has always been one), sometimes linked to administrative convenience (it's easy to organize)", etc. In our country, perhaps both the above mentioned reasons work behind the fact.

But, we must remember that learners' learning styles vary and the use of only one mode may bring boredom and reduce stimulation for learning among the learners in the classroom. Recently, criticisms of traditional teaching practices and evidences from research in *constructivism*, *information processing* and *cognitive development* firmly recognize that teachers need to involve students actively in the educational process itself in order to motivate and achieve more effective student learning. This represents a fundamental shift in educational paradigm from teaching to learning, in which students need to construct their own knowledge, understand the materials they are learning and to consolidate it within their own cognitive structures. Such an approach to learning is to enhance *deep learning* that may result in greater mastery of academic content. Students, therefore, need to be engaged in active-interactive learning during the instructional process itself in the class.

* Lecturers, Department of English, Daffodil International University, Dhaka.

2. What is lecture mode? And what is group mode?

Lecture has long been the standard mode of instruction everywhere, reinforcing “knowledge” as a “product” to be passed from the teacher to the learners.

Here the learners are perceived as empty vessels or blank slates to be filled with knowledge. The teacher is the main focus in the classroom activities and students turn to be passive observers in the practice of this mode. Friere (1972:45) calls this “Banking Education”, where the relation between the teacher (narrating subject) and the students (listening object) is passive, receptive, and the learner is uninvolved and isolated.

Group mode is distinguished from the lecture in the sense that while the latter is essentially a one-way process (lecturer-learner) and where students’ reaction is not usually welcomed, the former one is essentially interactive in nature. But, recent research findings advocate engaging students actively in learning through the use of a variety of teaching strategies in the classroom, such as, writing , discussions , case studies, and problem solving, which is possible only in group mode and not in the other one.

According to Wallace (1995), teaching and learning modes may be categorized according to their wide range of activities like tutor-learner interaction; tutor-control; attention to the individual; implication; scopes for expressions of feelings; physical organization of the classroom, and type of the source of teaching support. Actually, these are the criteria on which the perfection of any teaching mode is measured. But the fact is that the lecture mode is lagged behind by other modes in this respect.

A planned observation by these authors shows that nearly 80% of the class time in the universities is filled with teacher-talk and student note-taking. But, 100% of the students do not like their teacher lecturing the whole or most of the time during the class period without making any rapport or arranging discussion with them after the lecture. . It is to be noted that the observation took place at **Daffodil International University**, a recently established fast-growing private university in Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Purpose of the study and Review of the literature:

Practical teaching experiences at the university level have stimulated authors to look for the most apposite teaching modes as it is exposed that in all cases lecturing does not make the students responding properly to the desired teaching activity. In some cases, they are found not enthusiastic enough and a bit impatient to the extended lectures. So, it seems necessary to adopt efficacious teaching modes and strategies in respective cases. The authors believe that the most fitting teaching mode plays a vital role in the successful achievement of the learners’ pedagogic goal and the professional success of the teachers as well.

This is the age in which **cognitive researchers** are arguing that knowledge is not simply passed intact from the teacher to the learners in the process, but is actively constructed by the learners who draw on their previous knowledge, mental process, and experience to integrate new information into their knowledge base in ways that expand their knowledge and influence subsequent learning. **Constructivists** are saying that people construct their own understanding and knowledge of the world, through experiencing things and reflecting on those experiences.

Constructivist theory of learning views that when we encounter something new, we have to accommodate it with our previous ideas and experience, may be by changing what we believe, or may be by discarding the new information as irrelevant. In any case, we are the active creators of our own knowledge. They put forward that in order to do this, learners must **ask questions, explore, and assess** what they know.

But, we, in our country, are applying lecture mode as teaching scheme singly which leaves our learners as inert and memorizing machines. In most of the cases, learners cannot associate their previous and current knowledge and experience creatively as there is no hand-on-work activities that may help to assemble an “idea” and turn it into an “experience” just like an “input” turns into “intake”.

Argument may show that not all inputs remain unchanged in lecture mode and learners may learn by observing teachers “how to do?” But, the problem of “forgetting” cannot be ignored what can be avoided only in the construction of knowledge by the learners, own selves through accommodation and assimilation.

Several other researches have been conducted in this field. Some of them suggest guidelines for making the lecture mode a success, while some others made an attempt to show this mode in adjustment with some other common modes, such as, group work, pair work etc.

Barbara Gross Davis (1993) holds the opinion that lecturing is certainly something more than standing in front of a class and reciting what you know. She finds traditional lecture in failure and then specifies some general strategies for opening a motivating lecture, capturing students’ interest, closing a lecture successfully. In a study regarding active learning, Charles C. Bonwell and James A. Elison (1996) emphasize the importance of active learning in relation to lecture mode where they find that traditional lecture mode used singly leave the learners unable to respond properly in practical cases.

Matthew C. E. Gwee and Tan Chay Hoon (2001) conducted their research on the effectiveness of lecture mode in large group teaching and concluded that to deal with a large group of students teachers should go beyond the traditional way of teaching through engaging students in active- interactive learning, discussion, formal and informal small group dynamics. L. Dee Fink (1999) made a study on active learning and he found many college teachers desiring to move their learners from passive learning to active learning; he revealed a model for active learning which would constitute a set of learning activities.

But, this current study intends to compare the success and limitations of lecture as a traditional teaching mode in relation to those of different other teaching modes. It will expose the roles that other approaches may play in overcoming the barriers of lecture mode to turn it most effective for the students.

3. Advantages and Disadvantages of the Lecture Mode

The reason why lecture has long been treated as a standard manner of teaching is that it has got certain administrative advantages which lead us to acknowledge that it is really cheap in terms of human resources (one can address hundreds of people); the heightened and almost theatrical atmosphere of lecture may provide the lecturer with a chance to influence the learners and it is flexible as may be consisted, interrupted or followed by different other activities.

Some of the methodical strengths of lecturing include that the speaker can convey enthusiasm for the subject and can provide a role model of the scholar in action; lecture can convey materials otherwise unavailable, including original research or recent developments that have not yet been published; it provides organization, particularly, for students who read poorly or who are unable to organize print materials themselves; it is a bit low-risk situation for students, in that most of the activity is the responsibility of the instructor; it emphasizes learning by listening- an advantage for students who learn well in this way and finally, according to Brumfit (1983:203), only in a lecture can students be exposed to a demonstration

of the process of argumentation by one person, which can adjust itself to the needs and level of the audience according to its responsiveness.

Side by side, it is quite unavoidable that lecture mode has the weaknesses of *encouraging the receptive nature of lecture; excluding the experience of learners; not being well-studied for higher levels of learning, such as application, analysis and synthesis; assuming all learners at the same pace and same level of understanding which is hardly ever possible; being forgotten quickly.*

Besides these, Bonwell (1995) observes that, Relative effectiveness of a lecture depends upon the educational level of the learners; it is less successful with those who learn more proficiently through ways other than listening and lectures are less useful than active learning in promoting thinking or changing attitudes.

But, the most serious problem with lecture is the question of “**sustaining attention of the learners**”. Research shows that there is almost universally a drop in attention after fifteen or twenty minutes. This is termed as “micro sleeps”. Fifty or sixty minutes are a long time to spend for listening. Another major and unavoidable disadvantage is the **lack of feedback**. The lecturer can only guess the effect of his presentation on the learners very often.

4. Lecture Mode vs. Active Learning

A growing body of research has made it clear that the overall quality of teaching and learning is called improved when students have ample opportunities to clarify, question, apply, and consolidate new knowledge. These include improved critical thinking skills, increased retention and transfer of new information, increased motivation and improved inter- personal skills here.

In contrast to lecture style, “active learning” process gets students involved in more than listening, in higher order thinking (analysis, synthesis, and evaluation) and in activities (reading, writing, discussion). Besides, it has less stress on the growth of transmitting information and more on developing students’ skill and greater emphasis is placed on students’ exploration of their own attitudes and values.

What makes active learning different is the valuable contribution it has to develop the independent skills and ability to apply knowledge which is back footed in lecture mode as the latter helps the learners only to have **input** that may turn to **intake** but not to apply in practical situations.

A significant body of educational research deduces that the more dynamic involvement students have in the learning process, the more information they retain and the more enjoyable they find their experiences.

Utilizing an active and interactive teaching style may result in the paybacks like putting up own idea about the material; keeping hold of information longer; having familiarity in collaborating and cooperating with others through interactive processes; better learning in groups; enhancing self-esteem through class participation; having opportunities to clarify own beliefs and values; having increased incentive for future learning etc. to the students.

In one of the publications (1999), Organization of the Teachers of UNICEF suggests that by creating a fusion of different learning opportunities like **learning in groups** (pairs or small groups); **direct teaching** (lecture); **independent teaching** (problem solving), we can help learners to encounter new information, develop skills, try out ideas, and build knowledge.

This publication also suggests that we can persuade self-directed, independent learning in our classes by creating a learning environment that supports curiosity and focused activity, connecting new information with the information that has been learned previously, inventing assignments and learning activities that are meaningful to the learners involved and ensuring that learners are not afraid of trying out their ideas and exploring the unknown.

So far we have found that all views focus on the limited effectiveness of lecture approach, but not on its failure. Even not the field of **ELT** has discarded it totally. **A careful look into the notion of active learning or other teaching and learning theory provides the idea that single use of lecture form is discouraged while that of this mode followed or preceded by other student-participating modes are encouraged.**

5. Features of Group Modes

Some strengths:

1. Variety:

One of the main advantages of group mode is the rich variety of different kinds of activity it potentially encompasses. Some common types of group organizations are *Brain storming, Peer learning, Buzz group, Problem solving, Discovery format, Role playing, Debate, Learning cell, Case studies, Simulations, Demonstration or presentation, Discussion.*

2. Feedback:

Except *variety* and *flexibility*, a major advantage of the group mode is the feedback it provides which may take two different forms like *feedback to the teacher* and *feedback to the learners*. Teacher may make out the extent to which the material under discussion is pitched at the right level and is it obviously flummoxing the participants, or is it insufficiently challenging for the majority of them or not. Further, students may find it much easier in a less formal setting to get information from the teacher and also to clarify unclear issues with one another among themselves. There may also be feedback on the different levels of ability and different attitude of the group members that can help the students for successful completion of the course.

3. Reflection:

Group mode can provide ample scope for reflection, particularly in terms of learners being able to relate new information and ideas to their own prior knowledge and professional concerns. Discussion allows them to articulate their own perception of the new ideas, and practical sessions allow them to apply theoretical knowledge to realistic or quasi-realistic situations and to monitor the outcome.

Some flaws:

The most commonly recognized problem of group mode is that it may be expensive if the class is dominated by the tutor, with little space for learner-interaction when it becomes a time-consuming form of informal lecture. An opinion is often made by learners is that some sessions are aimless with no perceived beneficial result for learning often deserves grant.

Besides, some specific limitations of the different varieties of group modes cannot be often disregarded. For example, although **role play, simulation, or small group-works** endow with higher cognitive learning and direct own inquiry, it is time-consuming to sign and execute them and these sessions positively need greater care to be planned in effect. Though these are stirring and pretty clever to increase confidence level up, are all together difficult to be evaluated. **Discussion sessions** have a boon allowing learner to partake actively, to formulate and communicate questions and ideas but this method is also poorly effective in conveying

factual information. **Case-study method** has greater complexity and too much vastness in selecting, outlining, responding, scanning and describing materials what confines it within small classes only when it assists learners in applying lessons keenly. Objectives are often difficult to be understood in **simulations** while learning is generalized here from classroom to real-world. **Peer learning** may be absolutely helpful for some weak students, and also may become injurious when the partner suffers from ego or personality clash.

6. Group Work and Pair Work: Two Strategies in Implementing Group Modes.

There are many learning goals that can be achieved by having students collaborate either in *pairs* or in *small groups*. **Group work** promotes **participation** and **interaction** absolutely. It also fosters a deeper and livelier learning process. In addition to exposing students to different approaches and ways of thinking, working with other students in groups can promote a sense of fitting in to combat anonymity, isolation, or even shyness that often accompanies a student's experience in a large campus. Though it is not difficult or time-consuming to incorporate group work activities into our lesson plans, some general rules-of-thumb for structuring group work are there. In groups students can summarize main points, review problems, such as, for exams, compare and contrast knowledge, ideas, or theories, solve problems, or generate comments on class progress or on their levels of skill and understanding.

Pair work is another didactic strategy where students can be put in pairs for a great variety of work, including writing and reading. It is a good strategy as it endorses immediately an amount of student practice. It is demonstrated in many researches that having students work in pairs on a task is a low-risk strategy which virtually ensures 100% participation in classes of any size.

According to the purposes it is arranged for, pair work may be of different types like pairs sharing thoughts on a given materials, Question and answer pairs and Note-checking pairs. If we think of an imaginary class of forty students, pair work will have the force of involving at least twenty students talking at once instead of only one. The teacher will still, of course, be able to act as an assessor, prompter, or resource.

Which one to choose, *group work or pair work*? Let's try to find out the answer here:

In some ways, group work is more dynamic than pair work. There are more participants to react with and against in a group and, therefore, there is a greater probability of discussion is also there. An immense option that at least one member of the group will be able to solve the problem when it arises remains in a group, and working in groups is more relaxing than working in pairs, for the latter puts a greater demand on the student ability to co-operate closely with only one other person. Of course, the worries that relate to pair work apply equally to group work and one of the frequent setbacks for both the strategies is the selection of the group members. Group-size is slightly intricate. In general, it is safe to say that groups of more than seven students tend to be less than totally appropriate since the amount of student participation falls and the organization of the group itself may start to disintegrate. Pair work is a bit more sophisticated as it almost ensures the participation of both the students in solving the problem which group work provides the learners the scope for escaping.

So, the problem lies in both the techniques and which one is to be adopted depends on the material to teach and the activities the teacher wants to be performed in order to get the students involved.

Methodology:

The **methods** applied for the study included questionnaire, reflection of classroom experience noted in the authors' note book and individual and group interviews taken with a group of 100 students from each of the Under-graduate programs at Daffodil International University. The students were chosen from different levels; from 1st year 1st semester to 4th year final semester so that the related information on different subjects may not have any paucity of proper experiences. The subjects included students from BBA, CSE, CIS, ETE, Textile Engineering, B.Com (Hons.) and English departments so that a representative sample can be observed. The interviews were taken carefully with prior appointments and the students were treated cordially to make the goal of this step certain. The purpose of the interviews was explained well to each of the students in the classroom. Before they were provided the questionnaire they were convinced also by the idea that all of these steps were to make the teaching modes more effective, beneficial, and satisfactory for them. They took half an hour to think on the questions, to reflect, to consider, and to write down their comments. They appeared sincere enough during the interviews as the authors made the session lively and enjoyable for them. Apart from making written comments they expressed some points orally, which were recorded then. The subjects had no time limit to answer the questions and they responded to it in 20 to 30 minutes. The interview session lasted for 5-10 minutes with each of the students.

It is mentionable here that data and information were analyzed manually for this study.

Data interpretation:

Lecture:

95% of the students of ETE and CSE agree that only lecture does not help them at all to understand and build up their ideas properly. 25% find it helpful to some extent and only 7.5 % have expressed that it helps very little. On the other hand, 68% students of B.B.A. and B.Com (Hons.) program said that only lecture does not help at all them to understand and build up their ideas properly while 24% have informed that it helps to some extent and only 8% of them find it very little helpful in their understanding. Again, we get a different feature in English where 81% students think that lecture helps them to some extent; only 19% find it not at all helpful in building their ideas as it should be. Learners here further expressed that they cannot sustain their concentration on a long monotonous lecture in the whole period of the class duration and they have found that lecture provides only bookish knowledge and it does not let them test or prove their proficiency in the real-life situation. It is also exposed that they cannot understand everything properly through the lecture; most of the time what they get it through discussion among or between them and although it is very much helpful while introducing some new topics or materials, it comes of no use to have a concrete shape of that idea in oneself.

Discussion:

100% of the students have stated that it should be introduced in every course while they have it in only one or two courses like English-1(Language Composition) or Maths. All of them found it interesting and useful .78% of the respondents show that they welcome discussions among the students urgently to solve any problem or internalize something instead of one way communication of teacher's lecture in the class. About 70% of them emphasizes on the two-way communication between the teacher and the students frequently while they linger for the discussion among the students only when it is obligatory. They have also mentioned about the chaos created by the discussions among only the students.

Pair works:

It is disappointing to observe that the students of ETE and CSE, B.B.A. and English had pair work in only one or two courses - English-1 or Math while B.com (Hons.) had no pair work. About 90% students have stated that it is useful and interesting, but 51% have found it helpful usually and, rests 30% have found it so only sometimes. The remaining 9% have mentioned that it never appeared useful while 10% found it always necessary. The students found pair works as a break from the monotonous listening to lectures way of interchanging their own ideas and, thus, help each other. The respondents also pointed out the possibility and fact of completing the assignment own self by the strongly motivated student and remaining inactive of the other, the non-equivalent participation and imposing his or her personal ideas by the former student on the weaker and ignore the latter's one what discourage and interrupt their attempt to generate own view in solving the problem, presence of inadequate knowledge of both the peers to deal with the exercise. About 85% students desire to get it incorporated in every course.

Group work:

The respondents in our university have stated that they had group work in only two courses like English and Math-1 during the last summer semester which all of them found interesting and useful as they could exchange their knowledge and share responsibilities in groups in the classroom as well as out side .98% students of the faculty of science believe that group mode should be incorporated in every course while in commerce faculty the rate is 80%.16% have stated that it is useful sometimes and only 4% have found it unnecessary as they did not get any benefit from it. In English, 57% of them have welcomed it always while the remaining 33% expect it sometimes and 10% do not find any interest in it. Students say that, if group modes are utilized, they may get some grand plus like having refreshment and break in the monotonous listening to lecture, interchanging their personal views that promote their thoughts more rigorously, shaping own knowledge, creativity, and new thoughts practically, growing mutual help and cooperation which complete their partial thought through association and thus lessen their anxiety and feeling motivated for studying as it creates pressure on their minds as a prestige issue or competition. They also consent that group solutions that are often far superior to individual ones.

In spite of such reimbursements, there are some practical hurdles that originate sometimes because of the differences in attention and sincerity among the students that results a lack of understanding and mutuality, different opinions and shapes of thoughts of different students may create debate and confusion which only waste time instead of constructing a concrete idea, the tendency to gossip instead of studying, the force of some strongly motivated students to impose their own decisions on the less motivated and weak learners in which case the latter may suffer from feelings of being inferior. They also mention that only capable students may elicit the benefits if it is not properly investigated that all are participating and there are often inadequacy of space and proper physical arrangement for group work. The respondents comment that If the students are not properly cared and guided by teachers, they do not attain their own findings and understanding always confident.76% of the students of English have stated that group work should be introduced in every course while in science and commerce this figure is about 95%.

Presentation or demonstration:

The students of B.B.A and B.Com got presentation in most of their courses while those study English do it only once and students of other disciplines do not need to do it regularly. They have informed that it is quite helpful to demonstrate the lesson as they can have the reflection of both their academic and practical knowledge here. But, they have mentioned about some the limitations of the usual presentation done in the classes, which include space problem, English speaking problem, lacking of co-operation between students and the teacher, insufficient time allocated for each of them, nervousness, non-practical topics in some cases, and biased marking in some cases, etc. The respondents found it as a professional test and practice which is required to be performed more frequently.

Writing:

This finding has got a strange feature. Almost 57% of the students from each of the departments have agreed that they would like to write or have any writing assignment in the class always while almost 43% among those have informed that they like this sometimes. But, all the students think that writing in the class is quite supportive as it not only brings change in their monotony to hearing lecture but also provides occasion to have correction of their writing and ideas about the topic through checking. They also find a positive impression of marking that encourage them to perform better.

Brainstorming:

Brainstorming has got a substandard feature in this research. Only 38% of the students always want to find their brain exercising or storming for attaining some ideas always while 29% like often and 29% sometimes. And, some 4% never like it! They say that they do not get anything else doing this while others find it a must before any creative writing or debate in a language class or before any writing assignment in any theoretical class.

Role playing:

95% of the students of the department of English opt that role playing is absolutely needed in their language class, especially in the speaking class while 80% of them from B.B.A. and Textile Engineering welcome it. But, those 5% from English and 20% from other faculties do not discard this mode as they think these are helpful to some extent. Actually, they feel shy while performing anything in the class as they are not confident enough to speak in English before all. That's why, it is less beneficial to them. They also say that if it is practiced suitably, it would certainly elicit the best outcome from them.

Debate:

58% of the students from the observed departments prefer debate always in every course, while the remaining 42% like it sometimes specially in the language classes. Students here have made it evident that speaking is really thrilling and cheering and it gives one scope for presenting his/her own thoughts before the teacher and the peers and get recognition from them. It is also of a different taste which brings the learners curiosity back to the lessons. 100% students pick that they remain quit full of zeal before the debate class with their groundwork and argument!

7. Recommendations

Some recommendations are presented here that are supported by the findings of the study, students' conception, authors' experiences of teaching in the undergraduate programs, and some theoretical support from ELT literature. As the students are the prior concern in the study and "whether the hypothesis is null or valid" totally depends on their adjustment with and response to the applied teaching modes, learners' needs and requirements have been taken into consideration here.

What we find in our inspection and research is that learners do not welcome excessive authority of any single mode, like lecture or pair work or group work or writing or discussion. In order to get our educational and professional objectives and aims fulfilled, we would like to go for a principle one having amalgamation of different modes, upholding active learning properly and a meticulous support for learners' potentiality and stimulus. So, we recommend a **"Lecture that should be employed as followed by other active learning modes and the interactive modes which should not be introduced without preceding lecture"**

When and where to use lecture:

In any theoretical or practical class in any faculty- like science; business or humanities- lecture becomes a great way for providing factual information. It serves different other things like providing guidelines for the subject which is new; stimulating learners by posing an interesting problem; showing relevance of the topic to the professional concerns; contrasting and comparing two or more approaches; summarizing findings; listing a number of reasons, facts, etc; evaluating evidences; arguing a case; providing an overview of the subject.

We must deploy lecture to introduce and explain any topic to the students. It will put forward the content, idea, and theory of any topic and substance to the students. It guides them **what to learn, why, and how**. Moreover, lecture is the main way of communication and it conveys all message or instruction between the teacher and the students. We need to remember that lecture helps the learners to acquire knowledge as it is possible from books.

So, these unavoidable uses of lecture mode where it is needed and effective requires **some special cares** of the lecturer, it will maximize the advantages and minimize the disadvantages, like boredom, break of attention span, etc.

A. When preparing a lecture, the instructor should keep in mind that the learners' minds are not blank slates and that lecture should be connected with the previous lectures or some areas of existing knowledge or experience. That means the lecture should have **linkage**. It should define the elements of the key points and generate effective examples or analogies for each. Examples can both illustrate a particular point and broaden student's understanding of the subject. This will raise students' interest.

B. While opening a lecture, to avoid a cold start, the teacher may go to the class a little early and have some talk with the students using an informal voice which can help him keep his tone conversational. **A striking opening of a lecture** with a provocative question, startling statement, unusual analogy, personal anecdote, powerful quote, or a recent news event can grab students' attention which may work as warm-up too. S/he **must vary his or her opening of the lecture** as any dramatic technique may lose impact upon repetition. **Establishing rapport with the students** and its warmth will let them feel more engaged in the class if they find the atmosphere personal, direct and conversational. (Knapper, 1981)

C. At the starting, in order to capture the interest of the learners instantly lecturer can raise a question to be answered by the end of the hour. He may also provide a review of some

previously covered material to connect with the current lecture, explain the relationship between the lecture content and professional career interest, brief how they are expected to use the lecture material. Again, an instructor can start by telling a personal anecdote or a relevant funny story or by giving a lecture an integrating title.

D. A lecture with excellent content can easily be ruined by poor presentation. So, **while presenting a lecture**, the instructor should maximize the human contact aspect by eye-contact and a certain amount of gesture, varying voice projection, and fluctuation. Important ideas can be cued and emphasized by showing down, rising voices and repeating the points. Involving some interactive activities called “student participation”, like **buzz group, learning cell, discovery format, writing, brainstorming** etc. in the theoretical classes of literature, humanities and business faculty is must in order to overcome the problem of attention span. The students should have some easily explicable and specific task after 20 minutes or whenever the lecturer thinks his/her learners’ attention may be beginning to flag. Again, after five minutes, a few people can be asked to give their views, and their answers can be used as a link to the next section of the lecture. After finishing the lecture in about 30 minutes, lecturer may give the students a list; for example, of five or ten short questions to check their understanding (quiz technique).The lecturer may check the some of the answer sheets to get some feedback.

Consideration of these guidelines should not be taken to indicate that lecturing should be reduced to a formula. A limited variety in the organization and development of lecture is always needed to strike a balance between over predictable routine and creating confusion or uncertainty in the students’ mind.

Discussion:

Discussion is a must for conveying the newly-presented subject matter to the learners with a greater comprehension, to meet their related curiosity, answer their questions on the topic and to justify students’ self-generated ideas. Discussion between the students and the teacher may be either preceded or followed by the discussion among the students. In a language class, for example, the latter one which is held for problem solving or self internalization should follow the former one. But, sometimes in science classes after the discussion among the students, the teacher may have a short discussion with them to test and justify their thought. But, in any case, discussion among the students should be properly guided and taken care of by the teacher so that it is ensured that they are in proper track and that all are participating and that no unexpected chaos is there.

Pair work or peer learning:

Pair work may be arranged for either student’s own learning through exchange of their ideas after the lecture or in order to engage them in solving problem or doing exercises. These must bring back their confidence on and correction of their own understanding. While organizing pair work, the teacher must be alert to the type of activity the class is working with and he has to familiarize students with pair work at the beginning of the course by giving them very short, simple, task to perform; to ensure that every student is participating and only the strongly motivated ones are not leading the solution or understanding; take a decision about how students are put in pairs (he has to decide whether they will put strong students with weak students or whether they will vary the combination of the pairs from class to class); be candid with the students as to why you are asking them to do these things; remain at the front of the class to guide and observe all the groups equally without attending any particular one so that he can get the required activities done by the pairs and avoid noise and indiscipline.

Group work:

While organizing group work in the class, the teacher will take care of the points mentioned for the pair works first. Simultaneously, s/he must remember that a small number of learners are not interested in it that is first required to be motivated being engaged with an effective group. In order to get the expected result, the teacher has to guide the debate or confusion rose among them to the right theme and consult their decision or understanding so that they get the correct solution to match with their ones. Some bigger home assignment for more marks can be assigned in groups, but the number of the members should be limited and there should not be any group leader.

Writing:

Writing can be used in any class after lecture and discussion as a way of communicating and generating and incorporating new thoughts which can give the students a sense of active participants and performers .While the teacher will give writing assignment, it is not necessarily be formal or lengthy. The teacher may ask them to write a summary of the reading passage or to write down their thoughts after brain storming before they respond to a question or any short question answer. Another point to remember is that “not all the written assignments should be graded but all ones should be checked”. And, the results or mistakes should be discussed and reported as feedback.

Presentation or demonstration:

This mode should be introduced in every course and not once in a semester only. Better, it should be held each week once through a small report or research. The topic must be linked with lesson activities as a micro project of professional life. Here individual interest and potentiality should have been taken into consideration rather than giving an ordinary issue to all. The teacher must be quite comprehensive in his/her instruction and should give them keys in collecting information and analyzing and organizing data. While staging or demonstrating, the students may have a prescribed ambiance where there will be a panel of judges who may be the colleagues of the instructor so that they get a sense of authentic site. The instructor must care that the presenter experiences plenty of related questions to answer from the judges and other students. Scoring or marking should be neutral bearing no mark of teacher’s personal choice or students’ personality. Allotted time for the presentation or demonstration should be sufficient to make the idea and findings lucid.

Role playing:

It is a vital method to build up empathy and for providing concrete enactment of some abstract areas that should be dealt by the learners in order to expand competence practically, especially in the speaking classes. The teacher must provide ample information about milieu and the roles the students will play before their performance so that they can improvise proper dialogue and actions. In some cases of other theoretical classes with role playing students may be asked questions to answer.

Debate:

What the instructor can do here is that s/he must craft it at least once a week. In language classes it can be more frequent. After posing a debatable proposition, s/he will divide the class into two parts basing on the portions of those who agree and those who differ from it. It is quite important for the teacher to select the indispensable and effective propositions, enforcing students’ participation and summarizing the discussion and result of the debate. Some formal and assignment-based forms of debate may involve preparation of the students for at least a week in groups.

Brainstorming:

In any theoretical or practical or a language class, the teacher may appoint the learners in brainstorming to elude their instant thoughts roughly before any written or oral assignment. Whatever or how illogical first it may be, later it may be arranged in a proper way. This instant listing of thoughts gives the students a proper exercise format and helps to build up their knowledge and work.

8. Conclusion

In this age of learner centered approach, we must acknowledge that “.....the learners’ needs and wants tremendously control the whole package of teaching materials, aids and equipment, and the application of teaching techniques and strategies, the employment of classroom activities and, most importantly, the method of teaching and the construction of the syllabus.” (Fazlul Haque and Maniruzzaman, 1994:79). Although teaching mode is one of the major conditions of successful teaching where some other pre-conditions like teacher’s personality and professional responsibility, classroom management and educational skills and knowledge turn into some great factors in the classroom, selection of proper teaching modes and their appropriate arrangement and successful utilization is like the doctor’s prescription while others are like proper nursing for a patient.

This is quite a fact that we could not bring every thing like some personal strategies that some teachers may utilize effectively in their class duration and other points related specially in the field of ELT because we had a focus on all the students working in other courses also.

An observation of effective learning and teaching in respective classes has been done in this study keeping the same aspiration in mind. Instead of offering a new scheme or teaching method, we have strived to fit in some stimulating sorts into the customary lecture mode that can bring the learners’ impulse back while they fall in a “micro sleep” after every fifteen minutes while hearing lectures.

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Questionnaire

Name:.....

Subject:.....

ID:.....

Academic background: H.S.C / A level?

Lecture mode:

Do you like your teacher lecturing all of the time in your class without any discussion or rapport with you?

1. No 2. Very little 3. To some extent 4. Very much.

How long do you think your teachers delivery lecture in your each class?

- 1.100% of the class 2.90 % of the class 3.70 % of the class 4. 50 % of the class.

Dose only lecture help you to understand and build up the ideas properly?

1. Not at all 2. To some extent. 3. Very little 4. Very much.

Do you feel that there is a need of discussion among students or active student works or solving exercises in the class instead of one way communication of teacher’s lecture?

1. Yes, very much and always 2. No, not at all. 3. Sometimes 4. Very little.

pair work :

In how many courses you found pair works in your last semester?

Answer.

How much did you find it interesting and useful?

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1. Yes, very much and always 2. Not at all 3. Sometimes 4. Very little.

Did you find any limitations of pair work? If yes, what is that?

Answer.

Do you think that it should be introduced in every course?

Answer.

Group work:

In how many courses you found group works in your last semester?

Answer.

How much did you find it interesting and useful?

1. Yes, very much and always 2. Not at all 3. Sometimes 4. Very little.

Did you find any limitations of group work? If yes, what is that?

Answer.

Do you think that it should be introduced in every course?

Answer.

How can pair and group works help you? Do you find these better than hearing lecture all the time? Why?

Answer.

Others:

How much do you like that your friend will check your faults rather than your teacher?

Like strongly 2.like a bit 3. Dislike 4. Strongly dislike.

How much do you like enjoy brainstorming before any composition writing or comprehension passage?

1. Always 2. Often 3.Sometimes 4.Never

How much do you feel that role play is necessary in speaking class?

1. Very much 2.to some extent 3. Very little 4. Not at all.

How much do like writing as an active learning mode in the class?

1. Yes, very much and always 2. Sometimes 3.Very little 4. Not at all.

How much do you like debate in the speaking class?

1. Like strongly 2. Like a bit 3. Dislike 4. Dislike strongly.

Discussion:

How much do you like class discussion among students or between students and teacher?

1. Yes, very much and always 2. Not at all 3. Sometimes 4.Very little.

Which one do you prefer – “discussion among the students” or “discussion between students and teacher”?

1. First one 2. Second one.